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MODULAR OPEN SOURCE AUTOMATION KIT FOR AUTONOMOUS DRIVING BUSES

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ABSTRACT

Bus drop-off as well as bus periodic maintenance services are two of the tasks of transport companies where automation systems can increase the safety and the productivity. Bus drop-off is related to park the bus in companies' parking lot at non-working hours. At this time window other tasks are carried out as maintenance task. Both of them are activities that meet the requirements to be efficiently automated. In order to promote improvements and optimizations of these processes, the implementation of intelligent transport systems (ITS) is proposed, specifically, the use of autonomous vehicles. The technological base of autonomous vehicles is currently being developed. The currently available knowledge and applications allow already an almost immediate transfer to other sectors where the mobility requirements or the environment are not as demanding as on a public road in traffic, e.g. at the private facilities of the companies.

Under this scope, a deployment of the modular open source automated platform installed on a Tecnobus Gulliver U520-esp is presented, focused on the task of supporting future developments related to autonomous driving. This automation system has been designed, developed, and tested under real conditions in the facilities of a local public transport company.

The tests showed that the open source modular automation kit to transform conventional bus fleets into autonomous and connected vehicles presented by this paper can be seen as an important first step towards self-driving buses in real traffic. To achieve this, further development of powerful modules such as add-ons that allow for higher-level tasks such as perception and guidance will be necessary. By integrating these advanced modules, the automation kit will be able to perform more complex tasks and operate in more challenging environments.

Keywords:

Autonomous vehicles, autonomous driving, driverless, intelligent transport systems.

Research domain:

The work included in this paper is closely related to seminar's intelligent transport systems (ITS) & traffic management research topic.

1. INTRODUCTION

Car manufacturers as well as the rest of the participants in the automotive industry pursue the common goal of providing vehicles with a certain degree of autonomy, thereby improving both economic aspects (fuel efficiency, lower brake or tyre consumption, etc.) and social aspects (safety, comfort, etc.) (Weiskircher et al., 2017; Koopman & Wagner, 2017).

To a large extent, autonomous driving is framed within the framework of driving assistance systems on highways or in controlled environments. However, benefits from the experience within these areas can also help to make a smooth and evolutionary transition to other areas, such as agriculture, public works or off-road environments such as military surveillance, monitoring and rescue missions (Jiménez, 2018). In general, all these applications share the fact that there are tasks that present hazardous conditions for humans in addition to being well detailed, precise and repetitive.

One well-known and fairly well-developed example of autonomous driving is automated shuttles. They are an innovative solution for the mobility of people in a wide variety of spaces, such as city centres, towns, universities, corporate campuses, hospitals, parks, etc. Their main objective is to improve public transport by connecting centres and, in many areas, to provide a public service where there would otherwise be none. Autonomous shuttles are vehicles that can transport a small number of passengers at a time. They are designed to operate on predefined routes and at low speeds to ensure the safety of passengers and other road users. These vehicles are equipped with advanced technology that allows them to detect and avoid obstacles in their path. The implementation of autonomous shuttles can have several benefits for communities. Firstly, they can improve access to public transport for people with disabilities or physical limitations by providing door-to-door service. Secondly, they can reduce traffic congestion by offering an alternative to private car use for short trips. Autonomous shuttles can also improve operator productivity at private sites.

There are several companies and projects working on the development of autonomous shuttles. One example of this technology in action is the EZ10 vehicle developed by French manufacturer EasyMile (EZ10 Passenger Shuttle, 2016). The EZ10 is capable of carrying up to 12 passengers and continues to evolve, following predefined routes or working on demand via an app, detects and avoids potential obstacles with a full set of sensors. In Spain, this vehicle has been used, among other cases, on the campus of the Autonomous University of Madrid; in the Erica initiative in several Catalan towns; and it has served as the basis for the adaptation to the route of the Timafaya National Park.

Another example is the French company Navya, created in 2014. This company specialises in the development of autonomous driving systems, launched Arma as a fully autonomous, driverless, electric shuttle and first standalone production last mile passenger transport solution

(Navya, 2017). Similar features are offered by Local Motors' autonomous shuttle "Olli" (Whitehead & Hilton, 2018), Coast Autonomous Solutions (Haque & Brakewood, 2020) or Toyota's "e-Palette" (E-Palette, 2020), as well as multiple start-ups, and various European and national projects, such as 2GetThere (Das et al., 2017) in Germany.

Autonomous shuttles have a potential disadvantage which is that they have limited capacity: they can only transport a small number of passengers at a time. Additionally, the technology used in these vehicles is still relatively expensive and the initial cost of implementing a fleet of autonomous shuttles may be high. However, there are efforts to address these limitations. The study presented in this paper is an example. This study focused at the development of an open modular kit for transforming a set of conventional buses to smarter autonomous and connected vehicles, that could be operated both automatically or teleoperated from the headquarter. This type of technology has the potential to be more versatile and increase the capacity of autonomous shuttles while also potentially reducing their initial cost. This means that it is not necessary to purchase new vehicles in order to obtain the benefits of autonomous driving, but it is also possible to extend the useful life of the existing vehicles by providing them with powerful new functionalities.

This paper first presents the overall structure and the elements of the automation kit for public transport buses, and subsequently the results of some initial testing under real conditions in the facilities of a local public transport company.

2. AUTONOMOUS BUS PROTOTYPE

2.1. GENERAL REQUIREMENTS

The system developed is an automation kit adaptable to any of the buses in the current fleets of municipal public transport companies. Specifically, a Tecnobus model Gulliver U520-esp (Figure 1) has been used as a test platform and demonstrator. This system allows for the conversion of conventional buses into smarter autonomous and connected vehicles.

One key aspect of this automation system is vehicle control. The system must be able to control all aspects of the bus's movement, including acceleration, braking, and steering. This requires advanced technology such as sensors, actuators and algorithms on top of it. By integrating these technologies into an open modular kit that can be adapted to existing buses, it is possible to transform conventional buses into autonomous buses capable of safe and efficient operation.

Figure 1: Image of a Tecnobus Gulliver U520-esp

2.2. OPERATION

The automation kit consists of sensors, actuators and communication interfaces divided into independent modular subsystems. This modular design allows for flexibility in system configuration and expansion. The use of Ethernet connections ensures fast and reliable communication between automation kit and external components like PCs. The separation of low- and high-level tasks allows for efficient processing and decision-making.

Overall, this automation kit provides a comprehensive solution for various applications that require precise control and monitoring. Its modular design provides the foundation for advanced

algorithms making it a powerful tool for achieving desired outcomes in a wide range of scenarios.

Additionally, the automation kit allows for both autonomous control and preserving the natural capabilities of manual control without permanent modifications. This means that users have the option to switch between autonomous and manual control as needed. The system is designed to seamlessly integrate with existing manual controls. This flexibility allows users to take advantage of the benefits of automation while still retaining the ability to manually operate their systems if desired.

2.3. AUTOMATION KIT

System Architecture

The test bus has been subjected to the relevant electronic and mechanical modifications to enable the installation of the automation kit. The main components in which the kit interferes with are:

- The pedals of the vehicle (brake and throttle).
- The steering wheel.
- The gearshift controls.

As shown in Figure 2, the system architecture has been divided into three different subsystems or networks: one network relates to braking and steering, another to gear shifting, and a third to throttle operation. This division was necessary due to network saturation and incompatibilities of messages related to gear shifting and mass referencing between throttle operation and the main battery of the vehicle. The control of each of the components is performed through the CAN communications protocol, which is external to the vehicle itself.

Figure 2: Automation subsystems architecture

Steering automation

The steering control comprises a MAXON RE 35 electric motor and an electromagnetic clutch system that links the device to the steering column, as illustrated in Figure 3. The changeover from manual to automatic driving is carried out by activating the clutch, allowing the motor to act on the steering in the same way as a driver would. Thanks to this developed system (Jiménez et al., 2014; Jiménez et al., 2013), the independence and universality of the steering control module is achieved with respect to the platform used. For feedback and closed-loop control, a steering angle sensor is integrated into the steering column.

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Figure 3: (a) Steering control device, (b) Steering control system installed on the vehicle's steering column

Throttle automation

This test vehicle employs an electronic throttle system that regulates the power delivered to the engines. For this purpose, a device has been developed that receives CAN messages to switch between the line wired from the pedal (manual driving) and the line wired to the automation module power generator (autonomous driving). The power supplied to this cable is given by other CAN messages. Figure 4 shows the throttle control device. As mentioned above, the CAN message line of this device has been distributed in isolation from the rest, since its potential is not referenced to the rest of the systems.

Figure 4: Throttle control device

Brake automation

The conventional brake is activated by a pedal that the driver presses with the required braking intensity when the vehicle is in manual mode. To replicate this behaviour, a MAXON MCD EPOS 60W stepper motor assembly controlled by CAN messages has been installed (Figure 5). It pulls the pedal by picking up a chain, imitating the manual behaviour of pressing the pedal.

Figure 5: Brake pedal with installed braking device

Gear shift automation

When in automated operation, gear shift control in this test vehicle is carried out by switching between the digital signals from each of the positions available in the vehicle, which are: D - direct, N - neutral and R – reverse. A control card has been designed to switch the signals from the manually operated actuators (buttons) to the autonomous control signals. This is realised through a set of relays, which send the signal corresponding to each gear to the control unit. The system (Figure 6) is installed in the connector under the gearshift pushbutton panel.

Figure 6: Gearshift device

Subsystems controller

The control of the mounted subsystems such as power and control signals are distributed through a control case (Figure 7). Within the control case, there are two Gigabit Ethernet connections: one for a low-level PC and another for a high-level PC. The low-level PC contains algorithms responsible for computations between current state (received from sensors) and setpoints (determined from high-level PC) to govern control of actuators such as brake motor, throttle, gearshift or steering wheel rotation. The high-level PC contains more complex algorithms responsible for perception and localization. As shown in figure 2, it also has three different CAN bus interfaces. In addition, it also has the power management for each subsystem.

Figure 7: Control case of deployed subsystems

3. TESTING APPROACH AND RESULTS

3.1. TESTING FACILITY

In order to prove the correct operation of the automation kit developed, a validation with one prototype (Figure 1) has been carried out by performing a proof of concept test at the facilities of one of the local transport companies. A drop-off operation test as well as a maintenance operation test were carried out on the same day, in the morning, with sunny weather. Also, the tests were carried out while human drivers were performing their drop-off duties in the parking lots and relocating the buses that were in the establishment to the workshops.

These proof of concept tests were designed to see if our automation kit worked as intended and could be integrated into existing transport systems without causing any disruption or interference. By carrying out the test during normal operations, we were able to show that our kit could be easily installed and operated alongside conventional buses.

It is worth noting that for the tests, two systems external to the presented kit modules were installed. One of them was a GPS guidance system. The GPS system used in the tests is a satellite-based navigation system that provides location and time information. It uses a network of satellites to accurately determine the bus's location used to direct the bus along a predefined route to its destination. The second is a 3D LiDAR perception system. LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) is a remote sensing technology that uses laser light to measure distances and create detailed 3D maps of the environment. The LiDAR system used in the tests aimed to detect obstacles in the bus's path during the journey to avoid collisions and ensure the safety of staff at the bus premises.

3.2. TESTING DROP-OFF OPERATIONS

Once the bus has finished its working day and arrived at the entrance to the facilities, the automation kit will allow the driver to put the bus in autonomous mode so that it will follow the route to the designated parking lot on its own.

Such an automated drop-off operation frees up time for drivers to focus on other tasks and reduces the risk of accidents or collisions in busy parking lots.

The final parking maneuver is done manually by a trained driver who guides the bus into its designated spot. Once parked, the bus is plugged into an electrical outlet so that it can be charged overnight. This ensures that it is fully charged and ready for operation when it starts its next working day.

Figure 8: Drop-off operation. In green line is shown the reference route, in red, the followed route

Figure 8 shows the reference route (green) of the bus from the entrance to the parking lot as well as the actual route (red) during the test trial with the automation kit switched on. As can be seen the lines are almost completely overlapping, indicating that the automated function was performing as intended.

The top of Figure 9 (Figure 9-1) shows the targeted steering profile (blue) and the actual steering profile (orange). Again, both lines largely overlap, showing a good performance of the automated steering function. The two graphs below on lateral error (Figure 9-2) and angular error (Figure 9-3) reveal that currently the largest errors are found in the beginning of the drop-off operation. The error at the start of the run indicates that there is a mismatch between the bus position and the predefined route start, therefore, it has a large error that must be solved to align itself with the route. As soon as the positional mismatch has been resolved, the lateral error also shows some relatively small deviations during the second half of the operation, meaning that the route followed is close to the reference route. The angular error in the third graph refers to the difference between the actual steering wheel angle and the desired steering wheel angle when following the reference route. This graph shows the path followed, indicating a straight path with a small angular error and a curve with increasing angular error.

As regards speed behaviour (Figure 9-4), the targeted and actual values are close during the first two-thirds of the route. Towards the end of the drop-off operations, speeds are somewhat higher than targeted due to an increase in the bus's inertia on a downward slope. It is important to realise that the automated speed control has an acceptance threshold before acting on the

brake to correct the excess speed. Hence, as can be seen in the last one third of the route, there are ups and downs in the followed speed.

Figure 9: From top to bottom: (1) Steering profile, (2) Lateral error, (3) Angular error, (4) Speed profile

3.3. TESTING MAINTENANCE OPERATION

Once the bus is ready to be taken to the workshop for maintenance or repairs, the automation kit allows to put the bus into autonomous mode to navigate from the parking lot to the workshop on its own. Additionally, a V2X communication system is employed as a remote communication method to signal the bus when it needs to go to the workshop for maintenance tasks. Upon arrival at the workshop, a trained operator must carefully drive the bus inside the workshop. This ensures that it is properly positioned for any maintenance or repair work that needs to be carried out.

Figure 10: Maintenance Operation. In green line is shown the reference route, in red, the followed route

Figure 10 shows the reference route (green) and the actual route (red) for the test of the maintenance operation. Similar to the results of the drop-off operation the lines largely overlap indicating a good route guidance system.

Figure 11-1 shows the targeted steering profile (blue) and the actual steering profile (orange). One more time, both lines largely overlap, showing a good performance of the automated steering function. As shown before on the drop-off operation graph, this maintenance operation also starts with a mismatch at the start position of the bus with respect to the target route. Regarding the second graph (Figure 11-2), can be seen the lateral error committed due to the left-hand curves on the route, with the error being close to 0 on straight lines and increasing on curves. Regarding the angular error graph (Figure 11-3), it shows the impact on the angle of the bus steering wheel with respect to the trajectory. Since the lateral error is only a few metres in large curves, the resulting angular error is low, as expected. Finally, in the section from epoch

349 to 784, of the speed graph (Figure 11-4): it can be seen that the bus has a speed lower than the target speed because of an upward slope. Through the remaining part of the route, the speed of the bus is close to the target speed.

Figure 11: From top to bottom: (1) Steering profile, (2) Lateral error, (3) Angular error, (4) Speed profile

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the construction of an open source modular automation kit to transform conventional bus fleets into autonomous and connected vehicles. This modification will extend the lifetime of these vehicles and add powerful new functionalities that, among other benefits, will lead to economically more productive and hopefully safer intelligent transport systems.

The results of proof of concept tests show that the proposed automation kit to a large extent fulfilled its purpose of automating a conventional bus, making it possible to drive autonomously to a parking place and the workshop at the bus company's premises. The automation kit consisted of several components related to the pedals of the vehicle (brake and throttle), the steering wheel and the gearshift controls, it used advanced obstacle detection driving assistance systems (ADAS), as well as V2X communications, which are universally used in intelligent transport systems.

This study can be seen as a first step towards self-driving buses in real traffic. In summary, the next steps for the development of the automation kit will be to continue improving its capabilities and expanding its potential applications. The goal is to enable the transformation of larger vehicles, such as full-sized buses, into autonomous and connected vehicles. This will involve further development of powerful modules like add-ons that allow for higher-level tasks such as perception and guidance. By integrating these advanced modules, the automation kit will be able to perform more complex tasks and operate in more challenging environments. This will increase its versatility and make it an even more valuable tool for transforming conventional bus fleets into autonomous and connected vehicles.

Overall, the continued development of the automation kit represents an exciting step forward in the field of intelligent transport systems. By enabling the transformation of conventional bus fleets into autonomous and connected vehicles, it has the potential to revolutionize the way we think about urban mobility.

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